

Purification of ALK2, ALK2 GS loop mutant and SUFU

Proteins to be purified:

ACVR1Z-c110 (AKA ALK2 GS loop mutant)

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ*/SMTTNVGDSTLADLLDHSCTAGSGAGLPFLVQRTVARQITLLECVGKGRYG
EVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFRETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSLYDYL
QLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGTQGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCIALDLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNN
PRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDSYKRVDIWAFLVLEVARARMVSNQIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPSFEDMRKV
VCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSDPTLTSKAKLMKECWYQNPSARLTALRIKKTCLKID

ACVR1A-c096

MGHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQ*/SMQRTVARDITLLECVGKGRYGEVWRGSWQGENVAVKIFSSRDEKSWFR
ETELYNTVMLRHENILGFIASDMTSRHSSTQLWLITHYHEMGSLYDYLQLTTLDTVSCLRIVLSIASGLAHLHIEIFGT
QGKPAIAHRDLKSKNILVKKNGQCCIALDLGLAVMHSQSTNQLDVGNNPRVGTKRYMAPEVLDETIQVDCFDSYKR
VDIWAFLVLEVARARMVSNQIVEDYKPPFYDVVPNDPSFEDMRKVVCVDQQRPNIPNRWFSDPTLTSKAKLM
KECWYQNPSARLTALRIKKTCLKID

SUFU

Awaiting sequence from collaborators

*/ Indicates tev cleavage site.

Expression:

ALK2 Cells were expressed in Sf9 insect cells using baculo infection system. Cells were transfected and after 96h harvested at 900g for 20 minutes before freezing at -20 prior to purification.

SUFU was expressed in Rosetta DE3 E.coli cells at 37°C before induction with 0.4mM IPTG and growth overnight at 18°C

Purification:

For all samples

- Thaw pellets in luke warm water
- Sonicate ALK2 samples for 3 min (5s on, 10s off) on ice for baculo cells.
- Sonicate SUFU sample for 5 min (5s on, 10s off) on ice for ecoli cells.
- Divide each sample into two centrifugation tubes and top up with 'binding buffer' (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5) so each tube is full (aprox 40ml per tube).
- Add 1ml PEI (5%) per tube to precipitate DNA.
- Spin at 21.5k rpm for 1h.
- Incubate lysate with 5ml pre-equilibrated Ni-NTA beads at 4C for 1h. (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 5mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5)
- Spin down beads at 700g for 10 minutes to separate beads from lysate.

- Pour off lysate.
- Resuspend beads in 50ml binding buffer and load onto gravity flow column (collect flow through)
- Wash with 30ml wash buffer (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 30mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- **ALK2 GS loop mutant (ACVR1Z-c110)**
- Elute in 7ml elution buffer 1 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 50mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 3 x 7ml elution buffer 4 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- **All other samples**
- Elute in 2 x 7ml elution buffer 1 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 50mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Elute in 4 x 7ml elution buffer 4 (500mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 250mM Imidazole, 5% glycerol, pH7.5).
- Run samples on an SDS PAGE gel (mix 5ul of loading dye with 15ul sample, boil for 3 minutes and load 10ul onto the gel.) and run at 160V for 50 minutes.

Figure 1: SDS-PAGE gel of Nickel purification of ACVR1A-c096 ACVR1Z-c110 and SUFU showing flow through, washes and elution fractions. The red box indicates samples taken on for subsequent purification.

All samples

- Concentrate down relevant fractions to <5ml and run on a pre-equilibrated GF 75 column for all samples using standard gel filtration buffer (300mM NaCl, 50mM HEPES, 0.5mM TCEP, pH7.5).
- Collect fractions and run a gel of peak.

ACVR1Z c110

Figure 4: SDS-PAGE gel of ACVR1Z c110 gel filtration samples and corresponding UV traces from the AKTA runs using a GF75 size exclusion column.

ACVR1A c096

Figure 5: SDS-PAGE gel of ACVR1A-c096 gel filtration sample and corresponding UV trace from the AKTA run using a GF75 size exclusion column.

Figure 6: SDS-PAGE gel of SUFU gel filtration sample and corresponding UV trace from the AKTA run using a GF75 size exclusion column.

Figure 7: SDS PAGE gel of nickel rebind of ACVR1-c106.

All Samples:

Concentrate down purified fractions using a spin concentrator of appropriate MWCO (10KDa for ALK2/ACVR1 and 30KDa for SUFU) until high enough concentration (>200uM if possible) in the presence of 10mM DTT. Aliquot out and flash freeze in liquid nitrogen for storage at -80C or set up into crystal plates immediately.